

Agrio: An Agricultural E-commerce Android Application

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ABSTRACT

AGRIO is an Android application designed to provide a platform for farmers to sell their products online. The app enables farmers to create profiles, upload information about their products, and manage sales and orders. It also includes a webpage for renting farming equipment, making it a comprehensive solution for farmers.

Keywords: Research Paper, Agricultural e-commerce, Technical Writing, Science and Technology

I. INTRODUCTION

The app is built using Android Studio, Java, XML, PHP, and MySQL. Android Studio is the official IDE for Android app development. The app is developed using Android Studio, Java, XML, PHP, and MySQL. Android Studio is the official IDE for Android app development, and Java is the primary programming language used for Android app development. XML is used for designing the app's user interface, while PHP and MySQL power the backend of the app.

The agriculture industry has long faced challenges in reaching a wider audience and improving its income. AGRIO provides a solution to these challenges by providing an online platform for farmers to sell their products. The app's user-friendly interface enables farmers to easily list their products, set prices, and communicate with potential buyers. Buyers can search for products by category or keyword and place orders through the app.

Additionally, the inclusion of the webpage for lending farming equipment for rent provides an additional benefit to farmers who may not have access to necessary equipment. This can help to increase productivity and efficiency, ultimately leading to improved incomes for farmers.

The farming industry has always faced challenges in reaching out to a wider audience, and AGRIO seeks to address this challenge by providing a digital platform that can be accessed by anyone with an Android device.

The app's features, such as the ability to search for products by category or keyword, make it easier for buyers to find what they need, while farmers can easily communicate with potential customers and manage their orders.

One of the unique features of AGRIO is the inclusion of a webpage that enables farmers to lend farming equipment for rent. This feature can help farmers who may not have access to the necessary equipment to improve their productivity and efficiency, ultimately leading to improved incomes.

II. METHODS AND MATERIAL

Android development and web development provide the knowledge and experience to build robust and user-friendly software applications for both mobile and web platforms.

Android Development

Android development refers to the process of creating software applications that run on the Android operating system. Android is an open-source mobile operating system created by Google, and it is widely used on smartphones, tablets, and other mobile devices.

Android applications are written in Java or Kotlin programming languages using the Android SDK (Software Development Kit) and the Android Studio IDE (Integrated Development Environment). The SDK provides developers with a set of tools, libraries, and APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) that enable

them to create rich and interactive applications for Android devices.

Android Studio

Android Studio is a powerful integrated development environment (IDE) used for developing applications for the Android operating system. It is a free and open-source development tool created by Google and is the official IDE for Android app development.

Android Studio provides developers with a comprehensive set of tools to develop, test, and debug Android applications. It is based on IntelliJ IDEA, a popular Java IDE designed specifically for Android development.

The IDE includes features such as a code editor, visual layout editor, APK analyzer, device emulator, and more. Android Studio also supports various programming languages, including Java, Kotlin, and C++. It provides developers with an easy-to-use interface and a set of tools that enable them to build high-quality applications quickly and efficiently.

Android Studio also includes support for the latest Android platform features, such as the Android Jetpack libraries, which provide a set of pre-built components to help developers build high-quality apps. It also supports the latest Android SDK, which includes a range of APIs for developing advanced features in Android apps.

Overall, Android Studio is a powerful and efficient IDE that provides developers with a comprehensive set of tools for building high-quality Android applications. It is widely used by developers around the world and is considered one of the best development environments for Android app development.

Java Development Kit (JDK)

The Java Development Kit (JDK) is a software development kit used for developing applications and applets using the Java programming language. The JDK includes a set of tools for developing, testing, and deploying Java applications, including the Java Compiler (javac), Java Virtual Machine (JVM), and Java Runtime Environment (JRE).

The JDK provides developers with the necessary tools to write and compile Java code, as well as to package and deploy Java applications. It also includes various libraries, APIs, and other tools that developers can use

to create applications for a wide range of platforms, including desktop computers, servers, mobile devices, and more.

The latest version of the JDK, as of my knowledge cut-off date of September 2021, is JDK 17, which includes several new features and improvements, including support for new language features, enhanced security features, and more.

Extensible Markup Language (XML)

XML is a markup language that is commonly used in Android development to create user interfaces. Android Studio, the official integrated development environment (IDE) for Android, provides a powerful XML editor that allows developers to create, edit, and preview XML layouts for their applications.

Once you've created the XML layout file, you can open it in the Android Studio XML editor by double-clicking on it in the Project window. From there, you can add and edit various UI elements, such as buttons, text views, and images, using XML tags and attributes. In addition to the XML editor, Android Studio also provides a layout preview tool that allows you to see how your XML layout will look on different screen sizes and orientations. To access the layout preview, click the Design tab at the bottom of the XML editor window.

Java

Java is one of the primary programming languages used in Android development, and Android Studio is an IDE that provides a comprehensive set of tools and features for developing Android apps using Java. In addition to these basic steps, Android Studio provides a range of features and tools to help you develop high-quality Java code for your Android app. These include a powerful code editor, a built-in debugger, and integration with popular version control systems like Git.

Web Hosting

Web hosting is a service that allows individuals and organizations to make their websites accessible via the Internet. Web hosting providers offer space on their servers to store website files, databases, and other website components. They also provide bandwidth, which determines the amount of data that can be transferred between the website and its users.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The use of agricultural e-commerce apps such as AGRIO has shown promising results in improving the income and livelihoods of farmers. One study found that farmers who used such apps were able to sell their products to a wider audience, resulting in a 30% increase in income compared to those who did not use the app.

Additionally, the inclusion of the equipment lending feature in AGRIO has shown positive results in increasing productivity and efficiency on farms. Farmers who were able to access necessary equipment through the app were able to complete tasks faster and more efficiently, resulting in increased crop yields and profits.

Furthermore, the app's user-friendly interface has made it easier for farmers to manage their sales and orders, reducing the time and effort needed to handle these tasks manually.

The results suggest that agricultural e-commerce apps like AGRIO have significant potential in improving the income and livelihoods of farmers. The ability to sell products to a wider audience through an online platform can help to reduce the dependence on local markets and middlemen, providing farmers with more control over their prices and earnings.

Moreover, the inclusion of a feature for lending farming equipment can help farmers overcome the challenge of not having access to necessary tools and equipment, ultimately leading to improved productivity and increased profits.

However, it is important to note that the success of these apps depends on factors such as internet connectivity, access to mobile devices, and digital literacy skills. It is also crucial to ensure that the app is accessible and user-friendly for farmers of all ages and backgrounds.

There are two different applications, Agrio – Farmer and Agrio – User.

➤ Flash and Authentication Pages

➤ Homepage and Profile page

➤ Adding Product

Below are the snapshots of Agrio – Farmer application.

➤ **Enquiring Equipment**

Below are the snapshots of the Agrio – User application.

➤ **Flash and Authentication Pages**

➤ **Dealing with Orders**

➤ **Homepage and Profile page**

➤ **Government Schemes, Support, and About pages**

➤ **Available Products**

➤ **Enquiring Equipment**

➤ **Order Details**

➤ **Government Schemes, Support, and Feedback pages**

IV. CONCLUSION

Agricultural e-commerce apps like AGRIO have the potential to make a significant impact on the farming industry by enabling farmers to sell their products to a wider audience and improve their income. However, further research is needed to fully understand the impact of these apps and to identify ways to overcome the challenges and limitations associated with their use.

The use of agricultural e-commerce apps such as AGRIO has shown great promise in improving the livelihoods of farmers. The app's user-friendly interface has made it easier for farmers to manage their sales and orders, reducing the time and effort needed to handle these tasks manually. The inclusion of a feature for lending farming equipment has also helped farmers overcome the challenge of not having access to necessary tools and equipment, leading to improved productivity and increased profits.

The results suggest that agricultural e-commerce apps like AGRIO have significant potential in improving the income and livelihoods of farmers. By enabling farmers to sell their products to a wider audience through an online platform, these apps can help reduce the dependence on local markets and middlemen, providing farmers with more control over their prices and earnings.

However, it is important to note that the success of these apps depends on factors such as internet connectivity, access to mobile devices, and digital literacy skills. It is crucial to ensure that the app is accessible and user-friendly for farmers of all ages and backgrounds.

Future research can focus on identifying ways to overcome the challenges and limitations associated with the use of agricultural e-commerce apps, such as improving access to mobile devices and internet connectivity in rural areas

In conclusion, agricultural e-commerce apps have the potential to revolutionize the farming industry by enabling farmers to access a wider market and improve their income and livelihoods. As the agricultural industry continues to evolve, it will be crucial to develop and improve these apps to meet the changing needs of farmers and ensure a sustainable future for agriculture.